

Leadership competence and its importance in an educational institution

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance of leadership and leadership competencies in educational institutions. It describes how capable the leader is in finding solutions to problems faced in all areas of education. There is some information about the abilities, skills and knowledge that leaders should acquire. At the same time, it is aimed to improve the educational process and increase the quality of education in the educational institution through these skills and knowledge.

Key words: Leadership competence, leadership skills, educational management, educational quality, educational institution management, innovations, educational policy.

Аннотация: В данной статье подчеркивается важность лидерства и лидерских компетенций в образовательных учреждениях. В статье описывается, насколько лидер способен находить решения проблем, возникающих во всех сферах образования. Статья содержит некоторую информацию о способностях, навыках и знаниях, которыми должны обладать лидеры ацкойре. При этом целью является совершенствование образовательного процесса и повышение качества образования в образовательном учреждении за счет этих навыков и знаний.

Ключевые слова: Лидерская компетентность, лидерские качества, образовательный менеджмент, качество образования, управление образовательным учреждением, инновации, образовательная политика.

Introduction: The quality of educational processes in educational institutions is related to the level of management of the educational institution. Therefore, it can be said that the root of the educational policy is to be able to choose the head of the educational institutions and to develop his leadership skills and to improve the quality of education in the institution. In this way, it is possible to understand to what extent leaders work on leadership competencies in the development of institutions.

Research methodology: At a time when a lot of attention is paid to education policy in our country, we should not forget how important this policy is for our country, but we should not forget that this importance is primarily related to the management system of the education system. educational institutions and the leaders who lead them and this means that we now need to understand what is causing the current problems and find solutions.

At the current stage of the development of the educational system, it is necessary to change the management system from the administrative-command system to democratic and free-thinking forms. To overcome these problems, they must understand the true meaning of this skill during their leadership career.

And as a result, they will be able to predict the level of growth in educational processes through these management skills.

"Management - influences the system to ensure its quality and to regulate it in order to shape and develop it."

- In English - "management" means initiative, high professional training, organization, diligence.
- In Japanese - "management" means taking care of each employee, social security of production, desire to form, inner beauty.
- In French, "management" is the use of elements of human culture, high-level communication culture, national, historical, and cultural traditions to form a management system.
- In Chinese, "management" is related to Confucianism, is compatible with traditional values and modern management principles, and has an important role in the cultural and economic context.

In today's developing era, due to science, information and communication technologies, the level of importance of training leading personnel in our country is increasing even more. In this regard, with the initiatives of President Sh.Mirziyoyev, leaders are being seriously approached to work on themselves and to choose the right leaders.

The success of managing an educational institution is primarily determined by the personal, individual and subjective aspects of the head of the institution, which is represented by the "leader's management culture". Many studies have been conducted in this regard, and it is considered that "the success of the leader is the achievement of the institution".

There are basic principles in the management of the educational system, through which the management skills of leaders in all areas of education are increased.

- Democratization of management and recognition of humanity as the main place;
- Systematic and unified management;
- Coordination of center and region in management;
- Individual and team cooperation in management;
- Scientific basis of management;
- Completeness and accuracy of information in management.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a number of important decisions and proposals on the reform and improvement of leadership in educational institutions.

Improving skills and competence. As soon as the President started his work, he got acquainted with the work of the leaders in management activities and based on the mistakes they made, he introduced a system of continuous training for leaders and pedagogues of higher education

institutions starting from 2019. This process is carried out in regional and network centers in accordance with international standards.

Expanding autonomy. In recent years, by the decisions of our president, higher education institutions have been given powers such as independent decision-making, independent management of their income, setting quotas, selection of personnel, approval of educational programs and subjects, attraction of students from abroad. As a result of these powers, leaders began to work more on themselves.

Expanding responsibility. Based on the decisions of the President, the heads of educational institutions were entrusted with personal responsibility for increasing the efficiency of their activities and improving the professional training of students. In this case, leaders implement innovative projects and programs in cooperation with business entities.

Improvement of educational programs. Based on foreign experience, second foreign language and professional training modules are being introduced into the curriculum at the preschool, school, high school, and college levels. Heads of the institution are responsible for effective implementation of this process.

Summary. Leadership competence is a set of skills, knowledge and actions necessary for the effective implementation of the leader's activities in a certain organization (institution). These competencies are the ability of the leader to effectively perform management activities, to motivate and guide the team, to build relationships and manage relationships, to make decisions and to identify problems and find the right solutions. includes Institutions and organizations where a leader is able to develop such skills will prosper and continue to grow.

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